

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES IN THE FORMATION OF TEACHER SKILLS

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Abstract. This article reflects information on the role and importance of pedagogical abilities in the formation of teacher skills.

Keywords: constructive, organizational and communicative, academic ability, organizational ability, Gnostic ability, pedagogical and psychological nature.

РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ УМЕНИЙ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ УМЕНИЯ УЧИТЕЛЯ

Аннотация. В данной статье отражены сведения о роли и значении педагогических способностей в формировании мастерства учителя.

Ключевые слова: конструктивная, организационно - коммуникативная, академическая способность, организаторская способность, гностическая способность, педагогико - психологическая природа.

Pedagogical abilities, the so-called abilities, characterize both the mental side of the individual and the emotional-volitional side. All these qualities are interconnected with each other, affecting each other and dressing up one whole.

In psychology, abilities are defined as such: abilities are an individual-psychological feature that is considered a condition for the successful implementation of this activity of an individual and becomes inconsistent in the differences that arise in the dynamics of acquiring the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities for this. In pedagogical psychology, effective research has been carried out on the scientific interpretation of the role of pedagogical abilities in teaching activities. Senior psychologist S.L.As Rubinstein points out, the pedagogical process forms the personality of the child, which develops as the activity of the teacher-educator, depending on how much the educator is guided by the activities of the student or, conversely, does not need it. The role of the teacher in the development of the personality of the child benihoya is important, since it acts as the organizer of the educational and educational process. Therefore, in the current conditions, a high demand is imposed on the organizational abilities of the teacher, therefore, the wealth of socio-historical experiences directly depends on the increase in the scale of needs.

In the 70-80s, the character traits of the teacher, pedagogical abilities, the conditions for the content of educational skills in him were studied in depth.

In particular, the Russian scientist N.V.Kuzmina has carried out a number of scientific research works on the role of pedagogical abilities in teaching activities and their composition.

In his research, he described pedagogical abilities as

Gnostic (cognitive

Projective (focused on pre-planning)

Distinguishes it into constructive, organizational and communicative types, each of which indicates a deep psychological classification. N.V.Kuzmina also introduces observability, among

the important symptoms of pedagogical ability, these sensations of the teacher serve to identify factors such as the inner experiences, feelings of the student.

Major Uzbek scientist S.R. The work of Rajabov and hundreds of his students is focused on the pedagogical and psychological nature of the teacher.

Based on scientific research carried out in the field of pedagogy and psychology, it seems to us that the pedagogical abilities of a teacher can be classified as follows.

1. Didactic ability is the ability to explain complex knowledge to students in an easy way. It provides for the teacher to explain the educational material to the students in a clear and understandable way, to tell them the topic or problem, to arouse interest in active thinking independently in students. The teacher is able to change, simplify the educational material in cases where the need arises, make the difficult thing easy, the complex thing simple, incomprehensible, ambiguous.

2. Academic ability is the acquisition of certain knowledge on all subjects. A teacher with such abilities knows his subject not only in the size of the course of study, but much wider and deeper, monitors the innovations in his field of science. Science-Technology, Social-Politics study a lot with their interests in life.

3. Perceptive ability is the quality of being able to perceive the state of students in short moments, which is a psychological observation associated with the ability to enter the inner world of the student, the educator, to be able to very well understand the personality of the student and his temporary mental states. Such a teacher can also comprehend eye-progressing changes in the student's psyche on the basis of small symptoms, minor external signs.

4. Speech ability-compact, meaningful, melodic, speech with a certain rhythm, tempo, frequency; as well as the juxtaposition of the teacher's speech, its adherence to pause, logical stress, the speech of an able teacher will always be aimed at students in the lesson. Even if the teacher is explaining the new material, analyzing, approving or condemning the student's response, his speech is always characterized by his inner strength, confidence, focus on what he is talking about. The expression of thoughts will be clear, soda, understandable to the reader.

5. Organizational skills-the talent for organizing and managing a class-group or team. Organization is the basis for engaging students in a diverse range of activities. This ability is, firstly, the ability to organize, chipsize the team of students, inspire them to solve important tasks, and secondly, the ability to properly organize their personal work.

6. The ability to gain a reputation is the ability to build a reputation with his personal character, erudition, ingenuity, firm will. In science, this type of ability is also referred to as authoritarian ability. Prestige will depend on a whole complex of personal qualities of the teacher, on the willful qualities of the chunonchi, his will (boldness, endurance, rigor, exactingness, etc.), as well as on the feeling of responsibility for teaching and educating students, being able to convey this confidence to students as well.

7. Communicative abilities-the ability to establish treatment and communication, interfere with children, be able to find a way to approach students correctly, be able to effectively interact with them from a pedagogical point of view, the presence of pedagogical femininity.

8. Psychological diagnosis (diagnosis) ability-a person's prediction of the future, which consists in rational imagination. This is a special ability expressed in anticipating the consequences of their actions, in the upbringing and cultivation of a person, which is associated with the idea of

what kind of person the student will be in the future, in being able to predict what qualities of the educator will progress. This ability will be associated with pedagogical optimism, the power of upbringing, faith in a person.

9. The ability to distribute attention-to express its attitude towards several objects in one period itself. For the student, the teacher, it is important that all the features of attention-the size, its strength, portability, ability to handle and launch-are progressive.

A capable, experienced teacher carefully observes the content and form of the statement of the material, his own opinion (or reader's opinion), at the same time keeps all students in his attention, vigilantly observes signs of exhaustion, neglect, lack of understanding, does not neglect all cases of disciplinary violation, finally also monitors his own personal behavior (facial expressions, pantomimics, gait).

An inexperienced teacher often indulges in the articulation of the subject, during which time he ignores, loses control, goes and loses the calave of exposition if he tries to closely observe the students.

1. Constructive ability-the ability to plan educational work and predict the outcome. This ability allows you to design the development of the personality of the student, to select the content of training, as well as methods of working with students.

2. Gnostic ability is the ability to research and to verify one's activity, the process of this activity and its results, and to reconstruct activities in accordance with the results of the study.

It is also envisaged that the modern teacher should have in himself such abilities as the ability to wisdom of the mind, the ability to direct faith, an active life position, and to inspire initiative, creativity.

The comprehensive study of pedagogical abilities has shown that abilities consist in the manifestation of the qualities of the individual's intelligence, sense and will. Pedagogical abilities are associated with general abilities: for example, literary and scientific creativity, design abilities. They increase the effectiveness of the teacher's activities. Such teachers go to attract their students to this activity and achieve great success in providing them with education and upbringing. Pedagogical abilities are associated with character traits. Organization, rigor, truthfulness lead to an increase in the level of pedagogical activity, on the contrary, disorganization, indulgence, injustice reduce the results of pedagogical activity.

Each teacher will have their own individual-psychological qualities. Some of them are more mobile, others are more sluggish, some are tougher, others are softer. All these features are very good features, and the importance of their use is great.

From this, the teacher does not derive the meaning that emotions, emotions should be something foreign, but rather he can and should rejoice, be angry, Be Sad, be sad. Here it is not about the need for barovarization of the teacher to a person of some template (mold), but about his masterful use of his own individual qualities, the content of the necessary qualities of the individual in himself, the elimination of his own shortcomings. After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the task of achieving both economic and spiritual independence was put on the agenda before the people of our country. In Uzbekistan, as a component of the system of continuing education, the goal of general education schools and students is to freely develop the abilities and abilities that are present in every child, to learn the basics of science, universal and national – spiritual, cultural, values, to cultivate a high moral virtue, civic duty, a sense of national pride, to

direct young people to Scientific pedagogic research in the field of teacher etiquette, and practical work should be organized on the basis of historical experience of Uzbekistan and developed countries of the world.

Pedagogical ethics, historical experiments described above on teaching activities, scientific laws identified in this area, conclusions, which in the past justified themselves in the experience of different countries, scientific and moral rules, principles, norms, requirements, criteria-serve as a scientific and theoretical basis for the formation and improvement of the teacher's professional skills.

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